

APPLICATION OF MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS IN LOCATION SPECIFIC CROP YIELD PREDICTION

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Abstract: -

Food Supply Chain (FSC) is an essential service of a country to maintain a healthy population. Conventionally the FSC comprises production, processing, distribution and consumption phases. Modern technologies introduce one newfangled phase 'Yield Prediction'. Machine Learning is one of the progressive technologies which is used to assist human experts in several domains. The advancements in hardware and software engineering makes it possible to apply machine learning anywhere there is a requirement. This work named as "Application of Machine Learning Algorithms in Location Specific Crop Yield Prediction" is indented to investigate the latest innovative methodologies in Machine learning which can be accustomed to predict location specific crop yield prediction. The evolutions in Machine Learning makes it possible to handle massive data, thus the data analytics can be managed seamlessly. A comprehensive exploration is performed to evaluate most recent research works, methodologies used, advantages and their limitations in performing the crop yield prediction.

Keywords: Data Analytics, Food Supply Chain, Machine Learning, Yield Prediction

1. INTRODUCTION

Data are all around the world, and the massive developments in communication technology enable the collection and storage of these data in a feasible manner [1]. Processing these extensive data manually is merely impossible task. Machine Learning technology is the key to handle the prevalent data which can perform several

operations such as segmentations, exploration of behavior patterns, making recommendations, decision making and prediction [2]. Typically, there are four types of machine learning algorithms are in practice, they are Supervised learning, Unsupervised learning, Semi-supervised learning and Reinforcement learning. Supervised learning is applicable where the input data is continuous or discrete comes under the labeled category [3] Preparing the labelled training data requires manual operations. Supervised learning methods operates based on classification and regression. Unsupervised learning models work with unlabeled data. Unsupervised learning never needs human intervention between the processes [4]. Unsupervised algorithms work based on the principles of labeled and unlabeled data. Semi-supervised algorithms require human operations sometimes but not dependent always. It works based on classifications and clustering principles. Reinforcement learning is based is the positive or negative rewards acquired based on the actions over the training data [5]. Reinforcement Learning methods are best suited for performance maximization objectives. Agent, Environment, States, Actions and Rewards are the fundamental key elements of Reinforcement Learning. Reinforcement Learning is not depending on human interventions.

Agricultural production and agricultural yields are similar nevertheless not same. The production is measured based on the revenue generated by a unit of land. The yield is measured by the weight or quantity of the crop produced in a unit of land. Agricultural yield production is an essential responsibility to eradicate hunger. Crop yield production is a demanding composite process which involves several factors such as genotype of the crop, land quality, climate conditions, environmental elements and regional governance policies [6]. Since these factors are dynamic in nature, prediction of crop yield comes under the strenuous non-deterministic problem [7]. Fortunately, progressive technology advancements provide a way to approach the crop yield prediction problem and to find meticulous solutions.

As per the gathered literatures regarding crop yield prediction, Neural Networks (NN) [8], Linear Regression (LR) [9], Random Forest (RF) [10], Support Vector Machine (SVM) [11] and Gradient Boosting Algorithm (GBA) [12] are the mostly concerned methodologies. There are different versions of Neural Networks such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Deep Neural Networks (DNN), Modular Neural Networks (MNN), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Radial basis Function Neural Networks (RFNN) and Hybrid Neural Networks. Linear Regression models are split into Simple and Multiple linear regression types. A handful of variations of the above-mentioned methods are derived by several researchers to contribute towards crop yield prediction. A set of benchmark parameters are used to evaluate the performance of the crop yield prediction methods such as Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), R-Squared (R^2), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Square Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), Lin's Concordance Correlation Coefficient (LCCC), Multi Factored Evaluation (MFE), Simple Average Ensemble (SAE), Reference Change Values (RCV) and Mathew's Correlation Coefficient.

2. Existing Methods

A set of most recent endeavours towards contemporary crop yield prediction are chosen here to study the methodologies used, advantages and the limitations in detail. These works are selected based on the performance and their preamble period.

2.1 A Hybrid Approach for Crop Yield Prediction using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Algorithms (HACYP)

Sonal Agarwal and SandhyaTara[13] introduced a hybrid approach for crop yield prediction. HACYP method includes the soil ingredients such as Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potassium along with crop rotation, soil clamminess, environmental temperature and rainfall as the prediction factors. The combinational hybrid of SVM and RNN-LSTM is used to perform the prediction of several crops such as Rice, Wheat, Maize, Millets, Pea, Green gram, Soya beans and Sugarcane. HACYP work is compared with another hybrid algorithm that combines Decision Tree,

Artificial Neural Network and Random Forest. A dataset with Temperature, pH value, rainfall, area and relative humidity features is used from kaggle.com. The general Architecture of HACYP method is given below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: HACYP Architecture

It is claimed that the performance in terms of Accuracy is 97% achieved which is 4% higher than the compared existing method. Improved Accuracy is known as the advantage of this method whereas, the ensemble of SVM and RNN-LSTM provokes more processing time, which is the limitation of HACYP. Increase processing time accustomed slow training and testing process raise the compatibility issue while involving large datasets.

2.2. Crop Yield Estimation Using Deep Learning Based on Climate Big Data and Irrigation Scheduling(CYEDL)

KhadijehAlibabaei et al. [14] produced CYEDL work by combining two deep learning models, they are, Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Units (GRU). The motive of this work is to predict crop yield prediction using time series data that includes historical data, climate data, Irrigation intervals and soil humidity. The CYEDL work is a direct stack of standard Bidirectional LSTM and standard Bidirectional GRU models. The performance of this ensemble CYEDL is measured in terms of Mean Square Error and R^2 score.

A climate bigdata dataset from Portugal weather station is used to carryover the experiments. The dataset contains comprehensive data that comprises the minimum, maximum and average values of temperature, Relative Humidity, Solar Radiation, Wind speed and seasonal rainfall. CYEDL is measured with the MSE range between 0.0017 to 0.0039. The observed R^2 score is in the 0.97 to 0.99 range. The stacked BLSTM and BGRU architectures used in CYEDL work is given in Figure 2. Achievement of lower MSE and higher R^2 score is the noted advantage of CYEDL work, whereas, fewer number of features towards the calculation and higher processing time are constraints.

Figure 2: CYEDL: Ensemble of BLSTM and BGRU

2.3. Crop yield forecasting and associated optimum lead time analysis based on multi-source environmental data across China (CYFAOLT)

Linchao Li et al. [15] introduced a crop yield prediction method to handle multiple environmental sources such as climate, soil and vegetation of China. Random Forest method is used to create the CYFAOLT work. Since the work is location specific, entire dataset is collected from the China. There are two hyperparameter optimizations are performed to the standard Random Forest model as the contribution of CYFAOLT work. The range of tree is set from 200 to 1200 with step 200. Random samples are selected as the initial candidate for every tree split. Random Forest method requires bootstrap to construct the trees for which CYFAOLT method sets two third of data and the remaining one-third data maintained as Out of Bag data.

The multisource environment variable inputs are classified into six groups as T1 to T6 for every crop type separately. Then the forecasting events were executed for every growth stage and predictors were aggregated along with crop growth progression. The number of predictors are increased for every data group from T1 to T6. Important predictors are selected based on the relative importance of covariate. The performance of CYFALOT method is measured in terms of Normalized Root Mean Square Error (nRMSE). Lesser nRMSE is achieved in location specific crop forecasting which is the advantage of CYFALOT work whereas, too few decision factors and the absence of customary experimental results are the limitations of this work.

2.4. Crop yield forecasting using data mining (CYFDM)

Pallavi Kamath et al. [16] applies Random Forest technique to predict crop yields for specific region in India. Logistic Regression, KNN classifier and XG Boost classifier are evaluated along with Random Forest in CYFDM for prediction, in which it is stated that the Random Forest method achieved the higher accuracy of 98% for the applied datasets. A dataset with Climate variables and Soil agronomical parameters is used in the evaluation process of CYFDM. The Climate variables data contains details about Area, Temperature Rainfall and Humidity as well as the Soil agronomical variables data contains soil types of Chalky, Clay, Loamy and Sandy. CYFDM architecture is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3: CYFDM Architecture

Accomplishment of higher accuracy than the other methods in comparison is the advantage of this work. Location specific approach is also a added advantage which has a tangible impact in performance. Comparison with state-of-the art deep learning methods are not included in comparison. The yield prediction is performed only for a selected 100 acres land which is stated as the limitations of CYFDM work.

2.5. Deep Learning Based Wheat Crop Yield Prediction Model in Punjab Region of North India (DLWCYP)

Nishu Bali et al. [17] introduced a deep learning method in DLWCYP for crop yield prediction in Punjab, North Indian region. RNN-LSTM model is used as the core methodology of DLWCYP work. Artificial Neural Network, Multivariate Linear Regression and Random Forest methods are compared with the DLWCYP work. The target of the DLWCYP work is to predict the yields of notable agricultural districts in Punjab and Ludhiana states. DLWCYP method is designed with three primary modules, they are Data preprocessing phase, Training the prediction model and Validation of the Prediction model. The experiments are performed for the year 2021 in which the average temperature floats around 23.5 degree centigrade and the rainfall is about 876 mm. Standard version of LSTM neuron is incorporated with regular RNN in DLWCYP work. The struct of LSTM neuron is given in Figure 4.

Figure 4: DLWCYP LSTM Neuron structure

The performance in terms of Mean Absolute Error, Root Mean Square Error and Mean Squared Error. Achievement of lesser prediction errors is the advantage of this method whereas, consideration of confined parameters is the limitation of DLWCYP.

2.6. Deep machine learning with Sentinel satellite data to map paddy rice production stages across West Java, Indonesia (DMLSSD)

Indonesia is a country with rejuvenated agricultural schemes for a large number of strategic locations to constantly monitor and log data. By taking advantage of remote sensing technology, Indonesia implemented the state-of-the-art automation in agricultural data collection and logging. K. R. Thorp et al. [18] carried out a clear investigation on the performance of several machine learning algorithms for foretelling temporal progression of paddy rice yield. Unlike other common prediction methods, DLMLSSD uses satellite imagery data to predict the paddy yield. Different combinations of machine learning algorithms such as RNN, LSTM-RNN, GRU-RNN, CNN, CNN-RNN, Conv2D, Conv2DLSTM and ConvLSTM2D are examined in DLMLSSD work. Classification Indonesia's open access sentinel satellite imagery data acquired through Google earth engine to perform the experiments in DLMLSSD. Accuracy is taken as the primary performance evaluation parameter in DLMLSSD work. As per the observations of DLMLSSD work, Conv2DLSTM machine learning model scored higher Classification Accuracy Values. The architecture of Conv2DLSTM is given in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Conv2DLSTM Architecture

Utilization satellite imagery dataset is the contrast of DLMLSSD work whereas, moderate classification accuracy is the observed limitation.

2.7. Enhancing Crop Yield Prediction Utilizing Machine Learning on Satellite-Based Vegetation Health Indices (ECYPML)

Hoathi Pham et al. [19] introduced ECYPML work to make use of Vegetation Condition Index (VCI) and Thermal Condition Index (TCI) with machine learning towards crop yield prediction. ECYPML work is made up of three primary modules, they are, Higher order Spatial Independent Component Analysis, Combination of the principal component analysis and Machine learning module. The first module is developed to deal with the normal VCI/TCI spatial variability within their respective subregions and the combination of second and third model is used to improve the crop yield prediction accuracy.

Extraction of VCI and TCI data out of satellite data, Spatial independent component determination of subregions, Computation of average VCI/TCI time series for all subregions, Unbiasing Average crop production time series for all subregions, Division of Prediction / Response data into training and testing datasets, Development of crop yield prediction model, Training the model, and testing the model are the segregated phases of ECYPML work. The entire evaluation process of ECYPML is performed based on the rice production of Vietnam.

The performance of ECYPML work is measured using the RMSE metric. Tangible improvement in prediction error reduction is observed based on the experimental results which is the major advantage of ECYPML work. Although the accuracy is not up to the mark when comparing some deep learning models, which is the limitation of ECYPML work.

2.8. Exploration of Machine Learning Approaches for Paddy Yield Prediction in Eastern Part of Tamilnadu (EMLAPYP)

Vinson Joshua et al. [20] commenced a paddy yield prediction method for Cauvery Delta Zone, Tamil Nadu in EMLAPYP work. A set of machine learning algorithms for instance Support Vector Regression, Back Propagation Neural Networks, General Regression Neural Networks, and Radial Basis Functional Neural Networks are evaluated in EMLAPYP work. The achievement of these methods are analyzed in concern with Coefficient of Determination, RMSE, MAE, MSE, MAPE, Coefficient of Variance, and Normalized Mean Squared Error. The experimental data is acquired from a 14.47 lakh hectares geographical land located at the Cauvery Delta Zone, eastern part of Tamil Nadu. Temperature, pH value, Annual rainfall average, South-West monsoon, North-East monsoon and the type of filed are the utilized parameter to measure the performance of the above-mentioned methods.

Deliberate objectives such as Accessing the paddy yield information from potential rich locations, determining the paddy yield prediction using statistical model, incorporation of recent machine learning models in paddy yield prediction, and selection of best prediction method for paddy yield prediction are clearly approached in EMLAPYP method. As per the experiments performed in EMLAPYP method, it is stated that the General Regression Neural Network (GRNN) method outperforms the other methods in comparison. The architecture of applied GRNN in EMLAPYP work is given in Figure 6.

Figure 6: GRNN Architecture

Identification of GRNN as the well-suited method for paddy yield prediction is the prime conclusion of EMLAPYP work. Ensemble of more than one machine learning algorithms are not evaluated in EMLAPYP work which is known as the limitation.

2.9. Fuzzy Logic-Based Paddy Yield Prediction to Facilitate Weather Index-Based Crop Insurance (FLPYP)

The ultimate aim of FLPYP work brought by M. K. DulangaKithmini et al. [21] is to aid the agricultural insurance companies, though it is included in this survey work since the core concept is crop yield prediction. FLPYP is based on Fuzzy logic that operates based on the input parameters like Rainfall, Humidity, Temperature, sunshine hours and wind speeds. The experimental data used in FLPYP work are collected by Department of Meteorology originated in Kurunegala district of Sri Lanka. There are two separate prediction models framed in FLPYP work for crop yield prediction. The first one is a Three Rule Fuzzy logic which can predict the outputs into three categories such as poor, average and good. The second one is 5 Rule Fuzzy logic which can generate results in accordance with Very low, Low, Average, High and Very high categories.

Mean Average Error is used to evaluate the performance of the proposed modules in FLPYP work. The findings show that there is no significant difference between the 3 rule and 5 rule modules anyway, it is recommended to use 3 rule fuzzy system for crop yield prediction due to its reduced computational complexity.

The findings of FLPYP work states that the 3 rule Fuzzy logic system is preferable for crop yield prediction is the benefit of the work. The results produced by the tested models are not up to the mark while comparing with other machine learning models, which is known as the limitation of FLPYP work.

2.10. Hybrid Deep Learning-based Models for Crop Yield Prediction [HDLM]

In HDLM work produced by Alexandros Oikonomidis et al. [22], XGBoost, XGBoostRobustScaler, XGBoostRobustScaler and SelectFromModel, CNN-XGBoost, CNN-DNN, CNN-LSTM and CNN-RNN learning modes are evaluated. The performance evaluation work is carried out using Khaki and Wand dataset which contains details about USA geocentric Soybeans crop. The dataset contains different feature sets of Soil type, Weather conditions and management data. The soil dataset features are Wet soil bulk density, Dry soil bulk density, Clay ratio, Plant-available water content upper limit, Plant-available water content lower limit, Hydraulic conductivity, Organic element percentage, pH level, Sand portion and Dissolved Volumetric water content. The entire dataset contains 25345 samples with 395 features.

The architecture of applied machine learning models of HDLM are illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: HDLM Models

An apparent analysis over several machine learning algorithms and their ensembles is the advantage of HDLM work. RMSE, MSE, MAE, R^2 , Accuracy, Speed and Complexity are considered in HDLM work as the performance evaluation parameters. The experimental results shows that the XGBoostRobustScaler + SelectedFromModel ensemble method acquires higher performance in terms of Accuracy and processing speed. Application of Customized gates in RNN and in LSTM is not considered in HDLM work which is the limitation.

2.11. Integrated phenology and climate in rice yields prediction using machine learning methods (IPCRY)

YahuiGuo et al. [23] prepared a fair competition between Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) and Machine Learning (ML) algorithms in the process of rice yield prediction. The competitive prediction methods such as MLR, Backpropagation Neural Network (BPNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Random Forest (RF) are the methods are compared in IPCRY work. The experimental data is collected from 75 Agro-Meteorological Experimental Stations (AES) belongs to south China. The dataset features include *Oryza Sativa L.* (Rice) Sowing date (SO), Emergence (EM), Three Leaves (TL), Transplanting (TR), Turning Green (TG), Tiller (TI), Booting

(BO), Heading (HE), Flowering (FL), Milky (MI) and Mature (MA), Minimum Temperature, Mean Temperature, Maximum Temperature, Day-to-day Sunshine hours, Rainfall, Relative humidity average, Minimum relative humidity, Windspeed average and Maximum wind speed.

The experiments are performed to compute Mean Average Error, Root Mean Square Error and R^2 values. As per the observations made in IPCRY work, it is stated that the ML methods perform more than MLR methods. And while comparing ML methods, SVM and RF are outperforming the BPNN works. Implementations with more number of features is the known advantage of IPCRY method whereas, missing comparison of Deep learning methods is the constraint.

2.12. Machine learning for regional crop yield forecasting in Europe (MLRCYF)

DilliPaudel et al. [24] proposed a Regional level crop yield prediction using Multiple spatial levels. The conviction of MLRCYF work is to increase the support for national level crop yield prediction by deciding the regional level prediction results. A fair comparison between MARS Crop Yield forecasting system (MCYFS) and Machine Learning algorithms for regional and national level crop yield forecasting. The MLRCYF work includes 35 case studies of nine nations and six of their most cultivated crops. The countries assessed in MLRCYF study are Bulgaria, Spain, Germany, France, Italy, Hungary, Romania, Netherland and Poland. The examined crop varieties are Grain maize, Soft wheat, Spring Barley, Potatoes, Sugar beets and Sun flower. MLRCYF applies machine learning methods to reduce the Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE). The work extends by combining the regional level machine learning based forecasts to the national level. The considered features are Air flow, Temperature, Vegetation evapotranspiration, Shortwave radiation, Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation, Absolute crop areas (ha). Fraction of parent region's cropland, Total irrigation area, Crop specific irrigated area, Elevation, Slope and Water retention capacity of soil. The MLRCYF framework is given in Figure 8.

Figure 8: MLRCYF Framework

Ridge Regression, K-Nearest Neighbour Regression, Support Vector Machines Regression, and Gradient Boost Decision Trees regression methods are comprised in MLRCYF work. Prediction ability and uncertainty of regional forecasts, and Quality of National forecasts are curtly discussed in MLRCYF work. The implementation of MLRCYF work is performed using Apache Spark for pre-processing, Scikit learn python package for machine learning, and Bayesian optimization for hyper parameter tuning.

MLRCYF work concluded as the Machine Learning methods produce significant results in regional level forecasting while comparing with MCYFS. Essential features are used for the prediction in MLRCYF work which is

the advantage of MLRCYF. The prediction accuracy is comparatively frown while considering deep learning methods.

2.13. Predicting rice yield at pixel scale through synthetic use of crop and deep learning models with satellite data in South and North Korea (PSSDL)

SeungtaekJeong et al. [25] presented a Pixel Scale Synthetic Deep Learning model to achieve improved accuracy in crop yield prediction. The fact behind selecting pixel scale instead of Country scale is to acquire superior advantages of Crop management, crop yield response of various agricultural systems and Environmental factors. PSSDL work is the combination of pixel scale crop models and Deep learning models. The ensemble of LSTM and One-Dimensional Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN) operates based on satellite integrated crop models. In PSSDL, the performance evaluation is performed based on R^2 and RMSE metrics. Special parameters such as water index, temperature index, vegetation indices and Geographic variables of North and South Korea are interpreted in PSSDL method. Essential elements such as Pre-processing input data, Vegetation Indices and Transplanting date variable handling, Meteorological variables, Low land rice extent map of International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), and statistical rice yield reports are clearly discussed in PSSDL work. Remote Sensing Integrate Crop Model (RSCM) and Deep Learning Model are the core functional modules of PSSDL work. The workflow of PSSDL is given in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Step 1 and Step 2 workflows of PSSDL

Reduced R^2 and RMSE values are achieved in PSSDL work which is the tangible advantage as the same time, lack of inclusion of several essential input parameters such as soil types and location specific water retention capacity is realized limitation of PSSDL work.

2.14. The potential of remote sensing and artificial intelligence as tools to improve the resilience of agriculture production systems (RSAI)

The work of Jinha Jung et al. [26] is an honourable mention due to the endeavour of crop yield prediction with lesser manual intervention during the COVID pandemic situation. As the name suggests, RSAI work is combining the advantages of Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence. The RSAI method deals with the remote sensing data by means of Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS). An Amiable bridge interface is introduced in RSAI work to connect the Genomics and Phenoms with UAS. The genomics are used to analyze the crop biological process such as

growing speed, height of the plants and breeding which is used to balance the imprecise Z coordinate measurement of UAS images. A wide variety of crops such as Wheat, Soybeans, Maize, Citrus, Apple, Rice, Beans, Spinach, Banana and barley are included in the study conducted for RSAI work. The interface between Genome raw data and UAS image data is given in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Genome raw data – UAS Image data interface

The novelty of combining genomic data along with UAS image data for crop yield prediction is a fabulous attempt in the field of Agricultural research and development. The accuracy can be improved further by including more essential parameters and by applying efficient machine learning algorithms.

A table with the overview of existing methods, Methodologies used, Advantages and Limitations is given below.

Author	Work	Methodology	Advantages	Limitations
Sonal Agarwal et al.	A Hybrid Approach for Crop Yield Prediction using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Algorithms	SVM_RNN-LSTM	Accuracy	Processing time
KhadijehAl ibabaei et al.	Crop Yield Estimation Using Deep Learning Based on Climate Big Data and Irrigation Scheduling	BLSTM, BGRU	Lesser MSE	Fewer Features
Linchao Li et al.	Crop yield forecasting and associated optimum lead time analysis based on multi-source environmental data across China	Random Forest	Lesser nRMSE	Fewer Decision factors
Pallavi Kamath et al.	Crop yield forecasting using data mining	KNN + XGBoost	Higher Accuracy	Sample Area coverage
Nishu Bali	Deep Learning Based Wheat Crop Yield Prediction	RNN-	MAE, MSE,	Fewer

et al.	Model in Punjab Region of North India	LSTM	RMSE	Parameters
K. R. Thorp et al.	Deep machine learning with Sentinel satellite data to map paddy rice production stages across West Java, Indonesia	CNN, RNN, LSTM, GRU	Image Dataset	Moderate Accuracy
Hoathi Pham et al.	Enhancing Crop Yield Prediction Utilizing Machine Learning on Satellite-Based Vegetation Health Indices	VCI, TCI Extraction	Reduced Prediction Error	Moderate Accuracy
Vinson Joshua et al.	Exploration of Machine Learning Approaches for Paddy Yield Prediction in Eastern Part of Tamilnadu	SVM, BPNN, GRNN, RBFNN	GRNN Accuracy	Missing Ensembles
DulangaKit hmini et al.	Fuzzy Logic-Based Paddy Yield Prediction to Facilitate Weather Index-Based Crop Insurance	3, 5 Rule Fuzzy Logic	3 Rule Fuzzy results	Lesser Performance
Alexandros Oikonomidis et al.	Hybrid Deep Learning-based Models for Crop Yield Prediction	CNN, RNN, XGBoost	Higher Performance	Customized Gates are not used
YahuiGuo et al.	Integrated phenology and climate in rice yields prediction using machine learning methods	BPNN, SVM, RF	More Features	DL Methods are not compared
DilliPaudel et al.	Machine learning for regional crop yield forecasting in Europe	Multiple Spatial Prediction	Essential Features, Performance	Lower accuracy than DL models
SeungtaekJeong et al.	Predicting rice yield at pixel scale through synthetic use of crop and deep learning models with satellite data in South and North Korea	1D-CNN + LSTM	Reduced RMSE	Missing essential features
Jinha Jung et al.	The potential of remote sensing and artificial intelligence as tools to improve the resilience of agriculture production systems	Genomic Data + UAS	Lesser Manual intervention	Missing essential features

Table 1: Existing Methods Overview

3 Conclusions

There are several technologies such as Location specific feature selections, Satellite and UAS image processing and Genomic data integration are exploited along with various data science and machine learning models. Based on the observations, machine learning methods are producing more accurate results than the raw data mining methods. And the ensemble of multiple data mining methods along with machine learning algorithm combinations produce much more accurate predictions regarding crop yields. Every method has its own advantage of location specific precipitations and climate condition-based feature selections. As per the study performed on these methods, there is still a need for newfangled research works to deal with the crop yield prediction process to encounter the dynamic changing weather conditions and soil metamorphoses.

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